

The Influence of Green Initiatives on Customer Satisfaction of Health-Conscious Consumers in Sri Lanka

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Abstract

Eco-friendliness has come to be an essential aspect for modern businesses today especially for health enthusiasts and eco-friendly consumers in Sri Lanka. This research looks into how green practices like organic food production, eco-friendly packaging, organic farming, among others, influence customer satisfaction with specific reference to ABC Pvt. Ltd. in Sri Lanka. This research is located within a positivist philosophy and proceeds through a deductive strategy to verify the formulated hypotheses. It is a quantitative study whereby, data was obtained through a mono-quantitative survey strategy. The study was conducted cross-sectional, utilizing primary data gathered via questionnaires distributed to health-conscious consumers of ABC Pvt. Ltd. The sample was selected using convenience sampling, and 108 valid responses were analyzed using SPSS. Relationships between the variables in the study were evaluated through Pearson correlation and the influence of green initiatives on customer satisfaction was assessed through chi-square testing. From the findings, it can be concluded that there is a moderate positive relationship between the production of organic foods, the use of environmentally friendly packaging, organic farming, and customer satisfaction. The results of the Pearson correlation showed that eco-friendly packaging had the highest level of influence on customer satisfaction, so organic food and farming. These findings are consistent with the literature as they are adding into earlier studies reinforcing the importance of sustainable practices in enhancing consumer satisfaction, particularly for health-conscious individuals. The study concludes that green initiatives positively impact customer satisfaction, offering both theoretical and practical implications for businesses. This study adds to the growing body of literature on consumer satisfaction and highlights the necessity for businesses to prioritize green initiatives to foster customer loyalty and long-term success.

Keywords: Customer satisfaction, Eco-friendly packaging, Green initiatives, Health-conscious consumers, Organic food, Organic farming

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the study

The aim of this study is to examine the connection between green initiatives and customer satisfaction among consumers who are concerned about their health. The health conscious scope in Sri Lanka is progressively incorporating green practices to appeal to ecologically and health-conscious consumers as worries about the environment and personal well-being continue to increase. Nevertheless, little is known about the precise effect of these programs on the satisfaction levels of health-conscious customers, especially in the Sri Lankan context which mainly focuses on their green initiatives practices. Due to worries about pollution, resource depletion, and climate change, there is a global trend in many businesses towards sustainability. Organizations across several industries are embracing eco-friendly programs to lessen their ecological impact and conform to evolving customer preferences. According to Pronk et al. (2020), states that individuals who are concerned about their health give priority to goods and services that enhance their own health and wellbeing. Additionally, there's a greater chance that they care about the environment and the effects of their purchase decisions on the world. According to Alhulail et al. (2018), states that the customer satisfaction lies in its influence on consumer loyalty, recurring business, and favorable word-of-mouth recommendations. It is a crucial component of the success of a business. Gaining insight into how green efforts affect health-conscious consumers' customer satisfaction may be beneficial for companies in Sri Lanka looking to become more competitive in the market. By investigating the impact of green initiatives on the satisfaction levels of health conscious customers, this research wants to close the gap in the literature. This research will advance the knowledge of consumer behavior in the context of sustainability and offer useful advice to companies trying to connect with this powerful group of customers.

1.2 Research Objectives

Main aim of this research is to identify the influence between the customer satisfaction and the green initiatives in Sri Lanka.

RO1: To study the influence of organic food on customer satisfaction of the health conscious consumers.

RO2: To study the influence of eco-friendly packaging on customer satisfaction of the health conscious consumers.

RO3: To study the influence of organic farming on customer satisfaction of the health conscious consumers.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

A new generation of ecologically and socially concerned customers has emerged as a result of this model change of being health conscious due to the worldly issues such as resource depletion and climate change, and they are also health-sensitive. This research is conducted to find the influence of green initiatives such as organic farming, eco-friendly packaging and organic food produced by ABC PVT. LTD health organization in Sri Lanka and its influence on the customer satisfaction levels on its health conscious consumers. According to Huang et al. (2022), the coming together of these two key trends environmental sustainability and health consciousness has important ramifications for companies in many different industries, especially those in the retail and consumer products sectors. Businesses are under increasing demands to implement sustainable processes and provide products that complement consumers' ethical principles and lifestyle preferences.

2.2.1 Organic Food and customer satisfaction

Food that has been grown and processed without the use of artificial fertilizers, pesticides, or genetically modified organisms (GMOs) is referred to as organic food. Animal welfare, healthy soil, and environmental sustainability are given top priority in organic agricultural operations. Businesses that offer organic food demonstrate their dedication to ethical and ecological business operations. According to Ünal et al. (2019), organic items are prioritized by health-conscious consumers who believe they are better for the environment and healthier. Thus, companies who sell organic food are probably going to have a good impact on customer satisfaction when it comes to health-conscious customers. According to Wojciechowska-Solis and Barska (2021), states that a significant correlation was found between the tendency to purchase organic goods and environmental consciousness. This means that the health conscious customers will likely to buy organic products for themselves and their families, they believe

that plant-based substitutes, organic meals, and natural supplements are safer, healthier choices that in turn will also help increase consumer satisfaction.

2.2.2 Eco-friendly Packaging and customer satisfaction

Recyclable materials, biodegradable packaging, and less packaging waste are a few examples of ecofriendly packaging. Customers' preferences for eco-friendly items and their environmental ideals are in line with organic packaging. According to Bliumska-Danko et al., 2022, companies that use organic packaging demonstrate their dedication to sustainability, which appeals to customers who are concerned about their health. By enhancing favorable brand views, this alignment of principles and activities can improve consumer satisfaction. In a similar circumstance, the importance of eco-friendly packaging that helps to rise satisfaction levels of health conscious consumers is high, this is stated in the study by Brozović et al. (2021), as they say that that customers' decisions about which products to buy are influenced by the characteristics of certain packaging materials. Furthermore, the findings of their research shows that the characteristics that are categorized as appealing or one dimensional have a significant influence on the happiness of the customers. Similar to this, Rani (2021) states in their study that the influence of consumers choosing eco-friendly packaging over normal packaging to the growing concerns of the environment as an added concern over the health consciousness, the statement is reinforced in their study with the need to preserve the environment is becoming more widely recognized, which has caused consumer tastes to shift in favor of eco-friendly products.

2.2.3 Organic Farming and customer satisfaction

In organic farming, synthetic inputs like chemical pesticides and fertilizers are avoided in favor of ecological balance, biodiversity, and healthy soil. Ecosystem preservation, sustainable land use, and resource conservation are all aided by organic agricultural practices. According to Sukarno et al. (2022), companies that practice organic farming show their dedication to sustainable agriculture and environmental responsibility. Organic agricultural goods are seen as safer and healthier for consumption by health-conscious consumers. Thus, companies that engage in organic farming have a good chance of influencing the satisfaction of health-conscious customers. According to Lülfs-Baden et al. (2009), a correlation study demonstrates that customer enthusiasm is more accurate factor in the recommendations of shops that has

organic farming than customer satisfaction. Similar to this, according to, Prihartini et al. (2018), Customers' satisfaction and importance have demonstrated that the product's benefit, information, and substance are more important to them than its price and packaging. This means the relation with Organic farming and customer satisfaction of health conscious consumers is valid and is present.

Nisa et al. (2014), states in their paper that possible uses of organic farming as an agro tourism destination and for farmer entrepreneurship; to identify the characteristics of the current infrastructure; and to suggest some tactics for more sustainable development. Additionally, they claim that providing eye-catching agricultural attractions to highlight organic farming practices will increase the number of visitors and the duration of customer stays. On a similar note, another research by Priya and Ramesh Kumar (2019), states in their report that due to the negative consequences of inorganic food resulting from the extensive use of chemicals in farming, customer preferences and tastes have evolved in favor of organic food items, which has led to the expansion of the organic goods industry as well as the ways of organic farming which the consumers have a preference over to increase satisfaction levels.

2.2.4 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework (Author Developed, 2025)

2.2.5 Research Hypothesis

Ha1: There is a relationship between Organic Food and Customer Satisfaction.

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Ha2: There is a relationship between Eco-friendly packaging and Customer Satisfaction.

Ha3: There is a relationship between Organic Farming and Customer Satisfaction.

3. Methodology

This study aims to examine assumptions regarding how green initiatives influence consumer satisfaction of health conscious consumers in Sri Lanka, the research employs a positivist philosophy, placing an emphasis on objective, quantifiable data that helps in providing the research in measurable observation to be statistically analyzed. As the Research Approach the Deductive research approach is chosen as it starts with the formulation of hypothesis based on existing theories. Only quantitative data gathering and analysis are the emphasis of the mono-quantitative approach because the study approach is survey-based, primary data from Sri Lankan consumers who are health-conscious are gathered. This study also is cross-sectional in its time horizon, which means that information is collected all at once. Primary research via questionnaires (Likert scale) and secondary research via journal articles are both used in data collecting. The data analysis of the derived data between green initiatives and customer satisfaction are then determined by using SPSS. Descriptive analysis, along with Correlations and Chi square test has been done for the Hypothesis testing.

Due to the broader population of Sri Lanka, the scope population of this has been minimized to a single health centered organization, ABC Pvt. Ltd from which their customers that are environmentally concerned and prefer healthy products and services. The study's objective is to examine how green initiatives affect health-conscious customers' satisfaction, hence the population selection is closely related to the research issue. The total population size gathered over the course of a month at ABC Pvt. Ltd, amounts to 151. The 151 respondents' demographic is based on ABC customer database, which includes details on those who have done business with the company in the past month of March. The sample was gathered using the convenience sampling technique and the considered sample size is 108 which is in accordance to the Morgan table.

4. Data Analysis

4.1. Reliability testing

Table 1: Reliability Statistics Table

Reliability Statistics		
Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Organic Food	.807	5
Eco-friendly Packaging	.755	5
Organic Farming	.803	5

Based on table the Cronbach's alpha value for overall socialization-based questionnaire with fifteen statements received as 0.807, 0.755, and 0.803 respectively. As Cronbach's alpha is in the range of $0.9 < \alpha > 1$, the index is considered as highly reliable and can be accepted. This also means that all 15 items are consistent in their measurement of the concept, such as attitudes toward the influence between Customer Satisfaction and the green initiatives such as Organic Food, Eco-friendly Packaging and Organic Farming.

4.2. Inferential Analysis

Table 2: Inferential Statistics Table

Inferential Statistical Analysis		
Independent Variable	Pearson Correlation	Remarks
Organic Food	0.447	Moderate positive relationship
Eco-friendly Packaging	0.459	Moderate positive relationship
Organic Farming	0.420	Moderate positive relationship
Chi-Square Testing		
Independent Variable	Chi - Square	Remarks
Organic Food	0.000	Alternative Hypothesis accepted
Eco-friendly Packaging	0.000	Alternative Hypothesis accepted
Organic Farming	0.000	Alternative Hypothesis accepted

Based on the above summary, the Pearson Correlation values indicate the strength and direction of the relationship between each independent variable and customer satisfaction. For Organic Food, the Pearson correlation value is 0.447, which showcases a moderate positive relationship and the chi square test results further showcases the significance of this relationship as per the output of the test, the Pearson Chi-square value (p) is 0.000 for rounded three decimal points, therefore rejecting the null hypothesis and accepting the alternative hypothesis. This can be further proven by research done by Wojciechowska-Solis and Barska (2021), who also stated that there is a significant correlation between the tendency to purchase organic food and environmental consciousness of the consumers. This shows that using organic food in their products does have an influence in customer satisfaction.

Moreover, Eco-friendly packaging has a Pearson correlation value of 0.459, which is a moderate positive relationship and the chi square test result further showcases the significance of this relationship as per the output of the test, the Pearson Chi-square value (p) is 0.000 for rounded three decimal points, therefore rejecting the null hypothesis and accepting the alternative hypothesis. This is also highlighted in research done by Rani (2021), who stated in their study that the influence of consumers choosing eco-friendly packaging over normal packaging due to the global changing nature and the shift in consumers being self-aware about the environmental concerns. This further indicates that using eco-friendly packaging for their products does have an influence in customer satisfaction.

Organic Farming has a Pearson correlation of 0.420, which is a moderate positive relationship and the chi square test result further showcases the significance of this relationship as per the output of the test, the Pearson Chi-square value (p) is 0.000 for rounded three decimal points, therefore rejecting the null hypothesis and accepting the alternative hypothesis. According to Lülfs-Baden et al. (2009), customer enthusiasm is more accurate factor in the recommendations of shops that has organic farming than customer satisfaction. This indicates that having organic farming and sourcing organic products does have an influence in customer satisfaction.

Recommendations

- More focus on other operational aspects including the supply chain will also require in the future, and to be able to achieve the relative success on improvement must be internationalized. Educating customers on agricultural practices, certifications, quality

systems, and other aspects of their organic food product's source will earn the trust of a health aware market which is very concerned about their impact on the environment.

- The companies should make it apparent to the customers that they adhere to eco-friendly norms when it comes to packaging. This may be achieved through labelling, advertisement campaigns, and educational material that promote the sustainable benefits to the earth and health of people that the said packaging can deliver.
- Health focused Companies should seek to raise awareness among its consumers regarding the importance of using eco-friendly packaging alternatives. This can include description of proper disposal, recycling, and eco-harm reduction benefits from using green packaging.
- Organizations may further promote legislation that is in favor of organic farms and broad based sustainable agricultural practices in general. By doing this the business may participate with advocacy groups, trade bodies, and law makers to implement initiatives that support the development of organic farming, protect the natural environment, and promote regenerative practices in agriculture.

Conclusion

The results indicated a moderate positive relationship between all the three variables and the customer satisfaction which was measured through Pearson correlation and Chi square test. It can be stated that all of the factors studied in the research – organic food, eco-friendly packaging, and organic agriculture have strong correlations on customer satisfaction, where eco-friendly packaging can be said to have the highest impact. This explains the increasing trend in consumer sustainability that is emerging in Sri Lanka amongst the populations that are concerned with their wellbeing and seek for green practices. However, this research did face its limitations such as its scope and the time done to gather the data. To enhance the internal validity of future research, the future researchers can increase the sample size and employing a longitudinal study design to observe the effects of green initiatives that influences customer satisfaction.

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